

MATERIAL REMOVAL MECHANISMS OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES IN SINGLE DIAMOND GRAIN MACHINING

I. Sultana¹, Z. Shi², M.H. Attia^{1,2*}, V. Thomson¹

¹Mechanical Engineering, McGill University, Montreal, Canada,

²Aerospace Manufacturing, National Research Council Canada, NRC, Montreal, Canada

* Corresponding author (helmi.attia@nrc.ca / helmi.attia@mcgill.ca)

Keywords: *Carbon/Epoxy composite, single diamond grain, scratching, failure modes*

1 General introduction

This paper is concerned with experimental and numerical studies on the material removal mechanisms in single diamond grain scratching on Carbon/Epoxy composites. Machining of composites using single layer diamond tools is one of the most promising and effective techniques in terms of reduced cost, improved surface integrity, and extended tool life. To optimize the superabrasive machining process, it is imperative to have a good understanding of the fundamental mechanism of single diamond grain machining. Studying the single grain scratching provides the basis for modeling the machining process, which in essence involves the collective actions of numerous grains on the tool surface. Several studies on scratching tests were done focusing on *metal* removal mechanisms [1-4]. However, machining of *composites* is very different from metal machining. The non-homogeneity, anisotropic nature and different damage modes associated with composites make the machining process quite complex. As compared to the scratching tests on metal, studies on composites are very limited. Moreover, these studies were also confined to low speed machining [5]. This is because a diamond grain completes a scratch within a very short period of time in medium and high speeds. This complicates capturing the cutting phenomenon.

The finite element analysis carried out by Gao et al. [5] for the machining of composites by a single grain is based on micromechanics approach. The research was focused on the analysis of fiber failure mechanism when subjected to indenting velocity along the thrust direction. Several other finite element studies were, however, carried out based on micromechanics approach for orthogonal machining

of composites. In abrasive machining, it should be noted that a single grain may have very large negative rake angle with fiber orientation. In addition, all of these FE analyses were also limited to very low cutting speed to avoid the tendency of element distortion during simulation [6-8].

The present paper focused on the deformation mechanisms and composite failure modes during single diamond grain machining of Carbon/Epoxy composites with cutting speeds and feeds, comparable with those in superabrasive machining. Single grain scratching experiments were conducted using a geometrically well-defined diamond grain to explore the effects of fiber orientation on the material removal mechanisms. In addition, the material removal mechanisms in scratching with the slant face and the edge of the diamond grain were also studied.

A finite element modeling of the cutting process, based on the micro-mechanics approach, was also conducted to capture and reveal the failure modes of composites, as well as to estimate the damage level outside the machining zone.

2 Experimental setup

As shown in Fig. 1, the scratching tests were done with a diamond grain in a single point dressing tool, installed on a rotary disc, to simulate the cutting action of a single diamond grain. The geometry of the diamond grain was square pyramidal with approximately 2.58 mm grit diameter and 1.29 mm protrusion height, as shown in Fig 2.

Two sets of experiments were carried out to understand the deformation mechanisms of composites during single grain scratching tests. One set of tests included machining with slant face of the

diamond grain, while the other set included machining with the edge of the diamond grain. For both sets, unidirectional Carbon/Epoxy laminates with fiber orientations of 0°, 45° and 90°, with respect to the cutting direction, were considered. The cutting speed (v_s) was 15 m/s and the feed speed (v_w) was 300 mm/s. The depth of cut (a) was varied from 0.02 to 0.16 mm. The entire experimental work was performed on a 5 axis Makino CNC machining center. JX 71 Olympus microscope was used for optical microscopy of 0° machined samples.

3 Finite element modeling

In single grain machining or grinding of composites by superabrasive cutting tools, very small amount of material is removed by individual grains which requires much smaller element size in modeling. This, in turn, increases the total number of elements and significantly decreases the stable time increment in explicit FE analysis. Therefore, to avoid high computational cost, a small zone of interest was considered in the FE analysis, where the grain depth of cut is maximum, as shown in Fig. 3. At the maximum depth of cut, the grain has a tangential velocity that can be replaced by a horizontal velocity for this small zone. The workpiece feed speed is much smaller compared to the wheel speed and, therefore, can be neglected. The finite element model and the problem boundary conditions are shown in Fig. 4.

The workpiece was modeled as a layered material with fibers and matrix layers, backed up by equivalent homogeneous material (EHM). For 0° and 90° laminates, 7 fiber and matrix layers were modeled. For 45° laminate, 10 fiber and matrix layers were considered to ensure the initial cutting tool engagement into the fiber-matrix layered section instead of the EHM section. The material properties used in the FE simulations are given in Table 1.

ABAQUS 6.11-3 FE software package was used for modeling the process. The fiber was modeled as elastic and anisotropic material, while the epoxy was modeled as ductile and isotropic material. Cohesive contact was used to account for the interface interaction between a fiber and a matrix layer. The single grain was modeled with rigid elements without considering the wear of the grain. The tool-

workpiece frictional behavior was assumed to follow Coulomb friction law. For composite machining, the coefficient of friction can vary within a wide range, depending on the fiber orientation [8]. In this paper, the friction coefficient was fixed at 0.5 for carbon/epoxy workpiece and diamond tool combination.

3.1 Damage modeling

Damage modeling is an essential part of the analysis to establish the fiber and matrix failure modes. The primary scheme in damage modeling is damage initiation, which refers to the onset of material degradation at a material integration point. When effective stresses in a material reach the material strengths in the corresponding directions, damage initiation begins. This can be used in combination with damage evolution laws. Damage evolution capability enables the material to undergo progressive or gradual failure, whereas damage initiation without damage evolution responds only to sudden failure of material [9]. In this paper, damage evolution was used with damage initiation to model fiber, matrix, EHM and the cohesive contact.

Failure of the fiber material was predicted using Hashin's damage model, which considers four different failure modes; fiber tension, fiber compression, matrix tension and matrix compression. The following equations are used in Hashin's damage initiation model:

Fiber tension ($\sigma_{11} \geq 0$):

$$F_f^t = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{\sigma_L^t} \right)^2 + \alpha \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_L} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Fiber compression ($\sigma_{11} < 0$):

$$F_f^c = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{\sigma_L^c} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

Matrix tension ($\sigma_{22} \geq 0$):

$$F_m^t = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{\sigma_T^t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_L} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Matrix compression ($\sigma_{22} < 0$):

$$F_m^c = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{2S_T} \right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_T^c}{2S_T} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \frac{\sigma_{22}}{\sigma_T^c} + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_L} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where σ_{11} , σ_{22} and τ_{12} denote the components of effective stress tensor. The symbols σ_L^t , σ_L^c , σ_T^t , σ_T^c , S_L , and S_T refer to longitudinal tensile, longitudinal

compressive, transverse tensile, transverse compressive, longitudinal shear, and transverse shear strength, respectively. The variable, α , denotes the influence of the shear stress in the fiber tensile initiation criterion [10, 11]. In this paper, α was considered as 0, and the fiber shear strength was estimated as 50% of the fiber transverse compressive strength [10].

The damage evolution law for fiber reinforced composites is crucial in controlling the element deformation behavior. This law is based on energy dissipation during the crack formation process. Four energy dissipation parameters are used to accommodate the four different fiber failure modes, mentioned earlier. The following equations were used in this paper to estimate energy per unit crack length [9]:

$$G_L^c = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_L^c \sigma_L^c l_c \quad (5)$$

$$G_L^t = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_L^t \sigma_L^t l_c \quad (6)$$

$$G_T^c = \frac{1}{2} (\varepsilon_T^c \sigma_T^c + \varepsilon_S S_T) l_c \quad (7)$$

$$G_T^t = \frac{1}{2} (\varepsilon_T^t \sigma_T^t + \varepsilon_S S_T) l_c \quad (8)$$

where G_L^c , G_L^t , G_T^c , and G_T^t denote dissipated energy for fiber longitudinal compression, fiber longitudinal tension, fiber transverse compression and fiber transverse tension, respectively. The amount of dissipated energy is largely dependent on the mesh characteristic length, l_c . For shell elements, this length can be estimated as the square root of the area of the shell element.

A damage variable, d , estimates the extent of damage at a point in the material based on the damage initiation and evolution parameters and evolves from 0 (no damage) to 1 (complete damage). Only ductile fracture criterion was used for Epoxy damage modeling. This criterion predicts the onset of damage as a function of equivalent plastic strain, stress triaxiality, and strain rate. Evolution of damage was modeled using fracture energy to generate crack.

Table 2 shows the material strength and damage evolution data for fiber, matrix and EHM.

For both fiber and matrix material modeling, it is important to consider the mesh dependency of the damage evolution parameters. If the element size is too much reduced, the energy dissipated due to crack formation decreases significantly. This, in turn, creates sudden drop of stress at the point under consideration, and thus creates dynamic instability. Another important factor is to consider the ratio of the deformation speed to the wave speed. If an element is too small, the rate at which the element is deformed does not allow the stress wave to propagate through the elements, leading to mesh convergence difficulties. This creates a serious limitation on imposing high speed and feed conditions. To address these issues, mesh convergence analysis was carried out, and an average element size of 2.5 μm was used in modeling the fiber and the matrix to simulate 15 m/s cutting speed.

3.2 Interface modeling

Cohesive contact was used to model the interaction at the fiber- matrix, as well as the EHM-matrix interfaces. The elastic behavior of the cohesive contact was modeled with traction-separation law, where the material constitutive equation can be written as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} t_n \\ t_s \\ t_t \end{Bmatrix} = [K] \begin{Bmatrix} \delta_n \\ \delta_s \\ \delta_t \end{Bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Where, t_n , t_s , and t_t denote the normal, mode 1 shear, and mode 2 shear traction stresses, respectively. δ_n , δ_s , and δ_t are the corresponding separations. The matrix K contains the stiffness parameters, which are obtained from the contact element thickness, and the elastic and shear moduli.

A quadratic strain criterion was used as damage initiation criterion, where damage is assumed to initiate when a quadratic interaction function, involving the three separation variables, reaches 1. The damage evolution, used in this model, was based on fracture energies with mixed mode and exponential softening behavior. Mixed mode refers to the dependency of crack formation on fracture energy ratios: $\frac{G_n}{G_T}, \frac{G_s}{G_T}, \frac{G_t}{G_T}$ where G_n , G_s , and G_t are the energies required by the tractions and their conjugate

separations. Exponential softening indicates that the traction stress is exponentially reduced as the separation strain increases upon damage evolution [12]. Table 3 shows the cohesive properties used in the model.

4 Material removal mechanisms

In superabrasive machining of composites, material removal is largely dominated by fiber failure mechanisms. As fibers act as the main load carrying elements in composites, cutting force is primarily dependent on the fiber fractures. Fiber failure modes and fracture angles are again dependent on fiber orientation inside a laminate. Therefore, in the following sections, fiber failure modes of 0° , 45° , and 90° were analyzed with optical microscopy and simulation results.

To understand the dependency of material removal process on the grain orientation, machining by both edge and slant face of a diamond grain was carried out. However, no significant change was observed. In both types of machining, fiber failure modes were found to be identical.

4.1 Laminate of 0° fiber orientation

When an abrasive grain passes 0° laminate, a fiber is subjected to longitudinal and transverse compressive stresses as shown in Fig. 5. Both compressive forces crush a fiber at the beginning of machining (Fig. 6). However, since the fiber-matrix interfacial failure stress is much lower than fiber longitudinal compressive failure stress, a fiber tends to debond from its surrounding matrix before its failure. Due to debonding, this transverse compressive stress bends a fiber instead of crushing it, and thus generates bending stress along the fiber axis. At the same time, due to very high fiber length-to-diameter ratio, longitudinal compressive stress creates fiber buckling, as shown in Fig. 7. In either way, large amount of local bending stress is generated in a debonded fiber leading to fiber bending failure. This phenomenon is also apparent in optical microscopy of 0° laminate, machined by a single grain (Fig. 8).

A shear stress is also induced in a fiber due to compressive stresses. The level of the shear stress depends on the material properties. As a result, shear failure of a fiber is often observed in addition to pure

compressive failure, creating fracture plane angles other than 90° , as shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 10 shows fiber failure modes at a region outside the machining area. This was highlighted as side region in the figure. Fibers in this region are also subjected to transverse compression and fail by both fiber crushing and fiber bending.

FEA results of single grain machining of 0° laminate are shown in Fig. 11. It is clear from the figure that fibers start to bend as the abrasive grain approaches the workpiece, due to supporting matrix crushing. Bending stress generation and fractured fiber length were also highlighted in the figure. It was found that fiber fracture length varied from 0.01 to 0.04 mm, whereas in optical microscopy the fracture length varied from 0.011 to 0.016 mm. Fracture plane angles were varied from 58° (shear fail) to 90° (pure bending fail). Shear failure mainly occurred at the beginning of machining when an undebonded fiber was subjected to direct longitudinal compression. As debonding progressed, shear failure also transitioned to pure bending failure.

4.2 Laminate of 45° fiber orientation

During single grain machining of composites, a single grain follows a trochoidal path. The force exerted by the grain creates an angle with the fiber, which can be subdivided into two components; force acting along the fiber, F_L , and force acting perpendicular to the fiber, F_T (Fig. 12). In case of 45° laminate, F_L creates transverse tension due to Poisson's effect along with longitudinal compression. Since, transverse tensile failure stress of a fiber is lower than longitudinal compressive failure stress, fibers in a 45° laminate undergo tensile failure in the transverse direction.

It should be noted that the force component, F_T , creates transverse compression on the fiber. This leads to the crushing of the epoxy beneath the fiber, since epoxy damage requires low energy compared to fiber cracking. When the supporting epoxy completely fails, the fibers eventually find space for bending and thus fail by local tension and compression.

Fig. 13 shows the simulation results of 45° laminate during machining. Both the ductile damage of the epoxy matrix and the bending stress generation

along a fiber have been indicated in the figure. Fig. 14 shows the extent of damage for four different fiber failure modes (fiber longitudinal compression, fiber longitudinal tension, fiber transverse compression and fiber transverse tension) with the cutting time. It is clear from the graph that complete damage was obtained for both transverse and longitudinal tension indicating fiber tensile failure in transverse direction followed by bending failure.

4.3 Laminate of 90° fiber orientation

Similar to 45° laminate, the force F_L in the case of 90° laminate can cause a fiber failure by either transverse tension or longitudinal compression. However, unlike 45° laminate, fibers in 90° laminate do not fail by transverse tension. This can be explained by the fact that the contact area between a fiber and the grain is largely dependent on the included angle between fiber cross section and the grain slant face. Large included angle for fibers oriented at 90° leads to gradually increasing contact stress which, in turn, damages the fiber either by longitudinal compression or by shear. In 45° laminate, however, this included angle is very small, creating almost full contact between the grain slant face and the fiber cross section. This allows longitudinal compressive stress to act directly as normal stress, and leads to transverse tensile failure. The effect of F_T plays a key role in the failure of 90° laminate; F_T initiates fiber bending by epoxy crushing. Fibers act like cantilever beams subjected to transverse loading. Bending stress cause localized tension and compression, leading to fiber failure. Angle of the fracture plane with the fiber axis is dependent on the maximum deflection of the fiber.

Fig. 15 shows the simulation results of 90° laminate during single grain machining. It is clear from the figure that epoxy damage occurred, followed by fiber bending leading to fiber failure. Fractured fiber length was found between 0.008 to 0.025 mm, depending on the distance of a fiber from the grain. Fig. 16 shows the extent of simulated damage for four different fiber failure modes with the cutting time. The graph shows that the primary failure modes in machining 90° laminates are due to longitudinal compressive and tensile stresses.

5 Conclusions

The core objective of this research was to observe and analyze material removal mechanisms of carbon/epoxy machined by a single diamond grain. The following conclusions can be drawn from this study:

1. Material removal mechanism of composites depends on the fiber and matrix failure characteristics. As fibers act as main load carrying constituent of composites, energy required to fracture a fiber largely contributes to the required cutting force.
2. The dependence of primary material removal mechanism of composites on diamond grain orientation was found to be negligible.
3. Primary material removal mechanism for 0° and 90° laminates was longitudinal compressive or shear damage, followed by fiber bending failure. Shear damage was more dominant than longitudinal compressive damage as fibers are weak in shear. For 45° laminate, it is the transverse tensile failure that dominates over shear failure at the beginning of machining. As the grain advances, debonded fibers undergo bending and eventually fail.
4. From optical microscopy of 0° laminate, the fracture plane angle was found to vary from 56° to 86°, whereas from simulation, 58° was found for shear damage at the beginning of machining. 90° fracture angle was found for a bent fiber.
5. The length of a fractured fiber was found to be between 0.01 to 0.016 mm for 0° laminate. However, in the FE simulations, the fractured fiber length was found to be dependent on the distance of a fiber from its free surface and varied between 0.01 to 0.04 mm.
6. The fracture plane angle and fractured fiber length for 90° and 45° were not confirmed by microscopic examination. From the FEA results, fractured fiber length was found around 0.0175 mm for 45° laminate and approximately 0.008 – 0.025 mm for 90° laminate.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the financial support of Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council (NSERC). This research also benefited from the high performance computing facility provided by the CLUMEQ/Compute Canada Research Consortium. The authors also acknowledge the contribution of the National Research Council

Canada (NRC), Structures, Materials and Manufacturing Laboratory, where the experiments were conducted.

References

- [1] V. Singh, U.S.P. Durgumahnati, P.V. Rao and S. Ghosh "Specific Ploughing Energy Model Using Single Grit Scratch Test". *Int. J. Abrasive Technology*, Vol. 4, No. 2, pp 156-173, 2011.
- [2] L. Yan, Z. Zhou, F. Jiang, X. K. Li and Y. Rong "Grain-Workpiece Interaction Study of Grinding Process through Single Grain Cutting Simulation". *Key Engineering Materials*, Vol. 431-432, pp 269-272, 2010.
- [3] A. Zahedi and J. Akbari "FEM Analysis of Single Grit Chip Formation in Creep-Feed Grinding of Inconel 718 Superalloy". *Advanced Materials Research*, Vol. 325, pp 128-133, 2011.
- [4] W. Yu, Q. Feng and C. Ren "3D Finite Element Analysis of Pile-up Formation in Abrasive Machining at Low Speed". *Solid State Phenomena*, Vol. 175, pp 211-214, 2011.
- [5] Q. Wen, H. Gao, D.M. Guo and B. Wang "The Mechanics and Mechanisms of Material Removal in Abrasive Drilling C/E Composites". *Advanced Materials Research*, Vol. 325, pp 244-250, 2011.
- [6] K. A. Calzada, S.G. Kapoor, R. E. DeVor, J.Samuel and A.K. Srivastava "Modeling and Interpretation of Fiber Orientation-based Failure Mechanisms in Machining of Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Composites". *Journal of Manufacturing Process*, Vol. 14, pp 141-149, 2012.
- [7] G. V. G. Rao, P. Mahajan and N. Bhatnagar "Machining of UD-GFRP Composites Chip Formation Mechanism". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 67, pp 2271-2281, 2007.
- [8] G. V. G. Rao, P. Mahajan and N. Bhatnagar "Micro-Mechanical Modeling of Machining of FRP Composites- Cutting Force Analysis". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 67, pp 579-593, 2007.
- [9] *ABAQUS 6.11 Analysis User's Manual*, Vol. 3: Materials.
- [10] Z. Hashin "Failure Criteria for Unidirectional Fiber Composites". *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 47, pp 329-334, 1980.
- [11] Z. Hashin and A. Rotem "A Fatigue Criterion for Fiber-Reinforced Materials". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 7, pp 448-464, 1973.
- [12] *ABAQUS 6.11 Analysis User's Manual*, Vol. 7: Interactions.
- [13] C. Santiuste, X. Soldani and M. H. Miguez "Machining FEM Model of Long Fiber Composites

for Aeronautical Components". *Composite Structures*, Vol. 92, pp 691-698, 2010.

- [14] P. Linde, J. Pleitner, H. De Boer and C. Carmone "Modelling and Simulation of Fiber Metal Laminates". *ABAQUS Users' Conference*, 2004.

Symbols

E_1	Longitudinal stiffness
E_2	Transverse stiffness
ν_{12}	Poisson's ratio
G_{12}	Shear modulus
P	Density of material
σ_y	Yield stress
ε_p	Plastic strain
σ_L^c	Longitudinal compressive strength
σ_L^t	Longitudinal tensile strength
σ_T^c	Transverse compressive strength
σ_T^t	Transverse tensile strength
S_L	Longitudinal shear strength
S_T	Transverse shear strength
G_L^c	Longitudinal compressive fracture energy
G_L^t	Longitudinal tensile fracture energy
G_T^c	Transverse compressive fracture energy
G_T^t	Transverse compressive fracture energy
ε_f	Fracture strain
σ^*	Stress triaxiality
$\dot{\varepsilon}$	Strain rate
G_m	Fracture energy for matrix
EHM	Equivalent homogeneous material
v_s	Cutting speed
v_w	Feed speed
A	Depth of cut
σ_x^c	Longitudinal compressive stress
σ_y^c	Transverse compressive stress

l_c Characteristic length

Tables

Table. 1. Material elastic and plastic properties [5, 8]

	E_1	E_2	ν_{12}	G_{12}	ρ	σ_y	ϵ_p
Unit	GPa	GPa	-	GPa	Kg/m ³	MPa	-
Fiber	235	14	0.2	28	1800	-	-
Matrix	4	-	0.4		1600	85	0
EHM	155	3.02	0.246	4.4	1720	-	-

Table. 2. Material strength and damage properties

Fiber strength data [5, 8]					
σ_L^c (MPa)	σ_L^t (MPa)	σ_T^c (MPa)	σ_T^t (MPa)	S_L (MPa)	S_T (MPa)
1800	3590	2730	350	380	380
Fiber damage evolution data					
G_L^c (N/mm)	G_L^t (N/mm)	G_T^c (N/mm)	G_T^t (N/mm)		
0.13	0.260	0.82	0.14		
EHM strength data [13]					
σ_L^c (MPa)	σ_L^t (MPa)	σ_T^c (MPa)	σ_T^t (MPa)	S_L (MPa)	S_T (MPa)
1500	2000	200	50	100	100
EHM damage evolution data					
G_L^c (N/mm)	G_L^t (N/mm)	G_T^c (N/mm)	G_T^t (N/mm)		
0.091	0.16	3.33	0.0625		
Matrix damage parameters					
ϵ_f	σ^*	ϵ	G_m (N/mm)		
0.033	1	0.1	0.11		

Table. 3. Cohesive contact parameters [14]

Nominal strain Normal-only mode	Nominal strain Shear only mode First direction	Nominal strain Shear only mode Second direction
2.5 e-5	6.65e-5	6.65e-5
Fracture energy Normal-only mode	Fracture energy Shear only mode First direction	Fracture energy Shear only mode Second direction
4	4	4

Figures

Fig. 1. Experimental setup

Fig. 2. Diamond grit geometry (dimension is in mm)

Fig. 3. Modeling zone considered for FEA

Fig. 4. Finite Element model

Fig. 5. Stresses acting on a 0° oriented fiber

Fig. 6. Transverse compressive crack lines on fiber of 0°

Fig. 7. Buckling of a fiber

Fig. 8. Bending failure of a fiber

Fig. 9. Fracture angle of a fiber of 0°

Fig. 10. Fiber bending in side region

(a) Compressive damage at the start of machining

(b) Fiber bending

Fig. 11. Failure modes of 0° laminate

Fig. 12. Force components of a 45° laminate

(a) Bending stress generation in 45o laminae

(b) Fiber fracture mode of a 45o laminate

Fig. 13. FEA result of a 45° laminate

Fig. 14. Damage criterion evolution for 45° laminate

Fig. 15. FEA result of a 90° laminate

Fig. 16. Damage criterion evolution for 90° laminate